

**ABOUT THE LAST DAYS OF
MINISTER OF TURKESTAN NASIRKHAN TORA KAMOLKHAN TORAEV**

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Abstract. this article gives information about minister of Turkestan Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev and last days of his life. It is said that among the hundreds of patriots who battled for the Great Motherland known as Turkestan and lost their lives defending the independence of their people and nation, Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev's name deserves particular recognition. Through his many endeavors, this breed - one of the greatest religious academics and political figures - proved that he is the progenitor of Turkestan.

Keywords: Islamic education, Soviet government, Devmard, ghazal.

The name of Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev deserves special honor among thousands of patriots who fought for the Great Motherland called Turkestan and died for the freedom of the people and country. This breed, one of the great religious scholars and political figures, showed that he is the original child of Turkestan in his multifaceted activities.

Here is a short story about Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev. Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev was born in 1873 in the city of Koson, Namangan, in the family of a well-known madarris Kamolkhan Toraev. He first studied in Namangan and then Bukhara madrasas. He was a teacher in the Mawlawi and Mulla Kyrgyz madrasas in Namangan. In 1917, he was the head of the "Shurai Islam" society established in Namangan. Minister of Education of the Autonomous Government when Turkestan Autonomy was announced. After the government was drowned in blood by the Bolsheviks, it directly acted as a leader of the people's movement. In 1924, the property of Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev was confiscated by the state and he was sent to the house of correction (ispravdom) in Samarkand. In 1925, he was exiled to Orenburg for 3 years. When he was freed from exile in 1928 and returned to Namangan, the Soviet authorities were deeply worried by the non-stop visit of hundreds of people and the great reputation of Nasir Khan Tora at this level. They will strengthen its control.

This year, Nasirkhan Tora and his son Eshondadakhan will visit Chust, Bukhara, Kitab, and Samarkand. Nasir Khan witnessed the suspension of Hajj prayers and the closing of mosques for Muslims in the country during his tour of the Torah. He is afraid of the banning of Islamic education in madrassas and schools. In front of his students, he makes tearful lectures about the fact that if our children grow up with the current upbringing, the fate of the nation and ummah will become very sad in the near future. Also, he cannot bear the one-sidedness of the Shura economy, the sale of planted cotton for a pittance, the hunger of the markets, and the humiliation of the people under oppression. He writes a treatise on state administration in which the chairman and regional governors are elected, and assemblies are organized under them. According to it, the chairman and mayors take agricultural, tax and socially important decisions only with the advice and consent of the leaders of the assembly. There are twelve ministries in the country, each of them has a specific function. In particular, the Ministry of Education will reform education based

on useful and accurate sciences free from heresy and superstition. It organizes primary, secondary and higher education, and sets up the activities of textbooks and teachers. The main task of the political department is to protect the country and Muslims from various internal and external threats. He fights for real justice in society. He also outlines many of his proposals, such as a free press and tax cuts. Of course, the Soviet government did not like his hard efforts for the destiny of the Nation and the Motherland.

Now we will dwell on the facts and memories of the imprisonment and execution or death of this nobleman.

In the field of history, there are a number of researches covering the life path, scientific, creative and political activities of Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev, which serve as valuable information for introducing the owner of great potential to today's readers.¹ It should be noted that in most of these articles and studies, certain aspects of Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev's personality, scientific-creative and political activities are highlighted. However, the meeting of information related to the date of death of Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev in different forms shows that this issue has not been fully resolved. The act of clarifying and clarifying this information can be seen in D. Hamidov's article "About the date of death of the son of Said Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Tora". D. Hamidov analyzed a number of sources known and unknown to the public and tried to determine the date of death of Saidnosirkhontora Kamolkhontoraev by comparing the sources.² As D. Hamidov noted, "One of the reasons why Nasirkhan Tora's activities are not fully covered in the works created during this period is that the information about Nasirkhan Tora's personality and socio-political activities were classified in the archives of the Security Service of the Uzbek SSR and the USSR (OGPU-NKVD-MGB-MVD-KGB)"³, of course. "That's why today in our historiography, there are three different views about the date of Nasir Khan Tora's death: that he died in battle; that he was shot dead after the verdict; the facts that he died in Andijan prison approximately in 1930-1931 or on September 3, 1938 are known, and these facts deny each other"⁴ – emphasizes the need to clarify the date of death of this great figure. Despite the comparative analysis of a number of sources to shed light on the issue, probably due to the lack of reliable documents and evidence, this issue will not be resolved until the end.

It should be noted that the well-known scientist B. Irzaev in his article "Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Tora's son" clarified the issue on the basis of archival documents and facts. In this article, B. Irzaev, after giving detailed information about Nasirkhan Tora's life, social and political activities and works, mentions that Nasirkhan Tora was extremely persecuted by the Soviet

¹ Р.Шамсутдинов. Тарихнинг хасратли саҳифалари. –Тошкент:Шарк, 206. – Б.304. М.Х.Эрктурк, Р.Шамсутдинов. Саид Носирхон тўра – маориф вазири (1971-1938)// Водийнома журнали, 2017 йил №5 (7)-сон. Сирожиддин Ахмад. Вадуд Маҳмуд. Маърифат. 2008 йил, 23 август. Қ.Ражабов. Носирхон Тўра Камолхон Тўра ўғли.// Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси . Т.6. –Тошкент: “Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси” Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2003. - Б. 736. Мунаввар Қори Абдурашидхонов. Танланган асарлар. (Таҳрир хайбати: О.Шарафиддинов, Н.Аминов, Н.Каримовва бошқ.: Масъул муҳаррир Н.Каримов.-Истиқлол қаҳрамонлари туркумидан) – Тошкент:Маънавият, 2003.Б.304. Р.Акбаров. Туркистонда Бутунроссия таъсис мажлисига сайловларнинг ташкил этилиши (Фаргона вилояти мисолида)Ўғмишга назар. №10. (2020)Doihttp:dx.doi.org / 10-сон, 3 жилд. - Б. 7.

²Д. Ҳомидов. Саид Носирхон Тўра Камолхон Тўра ўғлининг вафоти санаси хусусида. Жамият ва инновациялар// 5 April 2021. 2181-1415/© 2021 in Science LLC.This is an open access article under the Attribution 4 International (CCBY4.0) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.ru>)

³ Д. Ҳомидов. Саид Носирхон Тўра Камолхон Тўра ўғлининг вафоти санаси хусусида. Жамият ва инновациялар// 5 April 2021. 2181-1415/© 2021 in Science LLC. This is an open access article under the Attribution 4 International (CC BY 4.0) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.ru>)

⁴ Д. Ҳомидов. Саид Носирхон Тўра Камолхон Тўра ўғлининг вафоти санаси хусусида. Жамият ва инновациялар// 5 April 2021. 2181-1415/© 2021 in Science LLC. This is an open access article under the Attribution 4 International (CC BY 4.0) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.ru>)

government and was captured in 1930 when he was trying to leave the country: "After not hearing from his friends, Nasir Khan Tora took his sons Eshondada Khan and Hasan Khan with him and decided to go to Kashgar. He appoints Eshondada Khan to follow his footsteps and meet him at Suleiman's tomb in Osh. However, the followers of the GPU captured Nasir Khan Tora on July 15, 1930, in a pasture 10-15 miles from Toldik state farm, Osh district.⁵

In the document published under the title "115 victims of repression who were not rehabilitated in 6 criminal cases were acquitted", we see that the date of execution of Nasir Khan Tora Kamolkhontoraev was confirmed as 1930⁶.

Now we will turn to the memories of when Nasir Khan Tora was imprisoned, the last months of his life and his sentence to death. According to the information given by Sirojiddin Ahmad, as mentioned in D. Hamidov's article, when Vadud Mahmud was in Tashkent, GPU officers M. A young student named Ismailov is attached as an "ear". In his letter dated February 14, 1931, that student reported: "Vadud Mahmudov, Saidnosir Khan and Kamolkhan are sitting in the same room with me..."⁷

In fact, Vadud Mahmud, one of the young authors of the literature of the 20s of the last century, was imprisoned for the first time on the back of various accusations against Abdulla Qadiri, Abdulhamid Cholpon, Abdurauf Fitrat, and was kept in the Tashkent prison for a while between 1930-1931. According to student M. Ismailov's testimony, the person sitting in the same cell as Vadud Mahmud was really Kamolkhan Tora Nasir Khan Toraev. Vadud Mahmud wrote down the days he spent with this great man in the form of a separate memoir under the name "Devvard" after his release from prison⁸. In the memoirs, there is no date about what year and in which months these events took place, but these memories match the dates given in the article by B. Irzaev, the events in the memoirs, the names and surnames of individuals and a number of other facts, and complement each other in certain places. Tora Kamolkhan Toraev's last months of life, the terrible days that befell him, and how he was killed, is a valuable source.⁹

Vadud Mahmud was released on January 26, 1954 after 20 years of consecutive exile and imprisonment. In one place, he writes that it has been two months since he received the certificate of release¹⁰. These memories about Nasir Khan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev were written down on May 27, 1954 in Samarkand. Based on this, it can be said that the first work that Vadud Mahmud wrote after his release from prison was Nasir Khan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev's memories.

First, let's talk about the reasons why these memories are called "Devvard". Some of the articles and researches about Nasir Khan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev published on social networks show pictures of Tora before and after his imprisonment.

⁵ Б. Ирзаев . Носирхон Тўра Камолхон Тўра ўгли. Jadidlar February 22, 2021. <https://telegra.ph/NOSIRHON-To'ra- KAMOLHON- To'ra-o'g'li-02-22>

⁶ Носирхон тўра (Насырхан Тюрса Саид Камалхон Тюроев) ва бошқаларга оид (92 нафар шахсга нисбатан) жиноят иши юзасидан. 1930 йил 27 октябрдаги суддан ташқари ОГПУнинг учлик мажлиси баённомаси кўчирмаси” <https://www.gazeta.uz/uz/2021/08/25/justify/>
⁷ Сирожиддин Аҳмад. Вадуд Маҳмуд. Маърифат. 2008 йил, 23 август.

⁸ Кейинчалик бу хотиралар Вадуд Маҳмуднинг ўғли Нажод Вадудзода томонидан кирилл алифбосига ўгирилиб, баъзи бир қискартишлар билан “Маъорифи омузгор” журналида чоп этилди. Вадуд Маҳмуди. Мужассамаи илму ирфон. Ёддошт. Маърифати омузгор // №11. 2018. С.57-61. Батгардон ва таҳияи Нажод Маҳмуди, Бахтиёри Абдурахим ва Муҳаммадшариф Рустамзода.

⁹ Вадуд Маҳмуд шахсий архивини ўрганиш жараёнида унинг Тошкент камокхонасида Носирхон Тўра Камолхон Тўраев билан танишувидан бошлаб то у кишининг ўлдирилишигача бўлган вақт мобайнида юз берган воқеалар қозғога туширилган қўлёзма манба билан қисқача танишиб, айрим ўринлари ёзиб олинган эди - З.Х.

¹⁰ Вадуд Маҳмуд. Шахсий архиви материаллари. Письмо Вадуда Маҳмуда неизвестному адресату.

The fact that the first picture is sharply different from the second attracts the attention of every reader. True, the appearance and health of a person who is unjustly imprisoned, crushed under various pressures, will certainly not be in good condition. But along with Nasirkhan Tora's appearance, certain changes are observed in his appearance. So that they would not recognize him, Tora changed his clothes to old peasant clothes, cut his beard short, and dyed it a little gray and white. This image of Tora is reflected in the second photo. According to B. Irzaev: "On July 7, 1930, he cut his beard and dyed it a little gray. Then he puts on old jackets and coats and sets off with Hasan Khan in peasant clothes¹¹.

In his memoirs, Vadud Mahmud described Nasir Khan Tora's appearance when he saw him for the first time: "It looks like he is over fifty. Big fat - tall, broad shoulders, short beard, gray hair, wide face, big eyes, arched eyebrows. He has an ugly cloth cap on his head, a cotton shirt on top, which is definitely dirty, and his feet are dirty." It also looks like... peasants¹². These sentences directly confirm the information given by B. Irzaev. So, it can be assumed that Vadud Mahmud Nasirkhan saw Tora in this way from the first meeting and because he was tall, handsome, and at the same time in old peasant clothes that did not suit him, he named his memories "Devvard".

Now about the issue of the year of imprisonment. As B. Irzaev wrote above, Nasirkhan Tora appointed Kamolkhan Toraev to "follow his footsteps to Eshondada Khan and meet him at Suleiman's tomb in Osh." However, the followers of the GPU captured Nasirkhan Tora on July 15, 1930 in a pasture 10-15 miles from Toldik state farm, Osh district.¹³

In one of the memories, V. Mahmud said: "In those days, they took out several people from each room at night and destroyed them. Most of them were figures of the national

¹¹ Б. Ирзаев . Носирхон Тўра Камолхон Тўра ўғли. Jadidlar February 22, 2021. <https://telegra.ph/NOSIRHON-To'ra- KAMOLHON- To'ra-o'g'li-02-22>

¹² Вадуд Маҳмуд. Ёддошт. Вадуд Маҳмуди. Мужассамаи илму ирфон. Ёддошт. Маърифати омузгор // №11. 2018. С.57-61.

¹³ Б. Ирзаев . Носирхон Тўра Камолхон Тўра ўғли. Jadidlar February 22, 2021. <https://telegra.ph/NOSIRHON-To'ra- KAMOLHON- To'ra-o'g'li-02-22>

movement, among them were the leaders of the national movement, Munavvar Qari and others.¹⁴ wrote that. According to the sources, Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov was arrested on November 6, 1929 and kept in Tashkent prison before his execution in Butirka prison in Moscow.¹⁵ The above sentences cited by Vadud Mahmud in his memoirs confirm that Munavvar Qori was kept in Tashkent prison for a while after his arrest on November 6, 1929, that is, the date was shifted to 1930. The second document is the Application written by Munavvar Qari on October 30, 1930 addressing the United State Political Department. It is said that he was kept in a single cell called "odinochka" for seven months and his health deteriorated: "Now I am very sick, my leg is swollen and I can't walk, I need help from others." Therefore, I request you to transfer me to a general cell or to hospitalize me."¹⁶ It is observed that the year and date indicated in the application are also consistent with the evidence in historical documents that Vadud Mahmud was in Tashkent at that time and the information he provided about Munavvar Qori.

In his article, B. Irzaev describes when and on what date Tora confessed to a series of "accusations" and signed the death sentence on the basis of these accusations in the following lines: they forced him to smoke. The reason for me to say this, despite the fact that a hundred years have passed since then, are those papers stained with the colors of my blessed tears.¹⁷

Vadud Mahmud narrates B. Irzaev's information in his memoirs as follows: "In the afternoon, they took him (Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev - Z.X.) upstairs again. After an hour he came back very depressed. Seeing him in this condition, I didn't even dare to ask him what happened. After a while, he said: "They read the verdict that I was sentenced to death." "I signed..." he said and fell silent."¹⁸

B. Irzaev says that GPU executioner Nasirkhan Torani was ordered to be executed on October 27, 1930. But this sentence was executed on April 13, 1931. Why was Torah executed almost six months after the appointed time?! - the question arises. Wadud Mahmud's memoirs clarify the real reason for this issue.

After hearing the terrible news that Nasir Khan Tora was sentenced to death, Vadud Mahmud says that he wrote a ghazal-lament dedicated to the death of Nasir Khan Tora and read it to Nasir Khan Tora himself. Abdullajan Eshon from Andijan tied a mukhammas to the ghazal, and this mukhammas quickly became popular among the prisoners and caused a lot of commotion. As a result, the prison guards began to re-arrest all the prisoners. Many captives were sent to remote areas of the landless country.

In fact, Vadud Mahmud did not write a dirge dedicated to the death of this person for nothing, Abdullajan did not attach a hymn to this ghazal for nothing, this hymn spread throughout the prison did not worry the prison guards for nothing, and finally, the prisoners who read and distributed this poem were re-imprisoned and sent to distant places in difficult conditions. they did not send... Because Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev was the symbol and pride of Turkestan, this nation. Therefore, the prison authorities were afraid that the news that Nasirkhan Toraday was

¹⁴ Вадуд Махмуд. Девмард. Қўлэзма манба. 8-бет.

¹⁵ <https://ziyouz.uz/uzbek-ziyolilari/munavvar-qori-abdurashidxon/>

¹⁶ https://docs.yandex.ru/docs/Munavvar_qori.Tanlangan_asarlar.pdf. Нашрга тайёрловчи ва сўзбоши муаллифи Сирожиддин Ахмад. – Тошкент: Маънавият. 2003, 57 –бет.

¹⁷ Б. Ирзаев . Носирхон Тўра Камолхон Тўра ўғли. Jadidlar February 22, 2021. <https://tegra.ph/NOSIRHON-To'ra-KAMOLHON-To'ra-o'g'li-02-22>

¹⁸ Вадуд Махмуд. Ёддошт. Вадуд Махмуди. Мужассамаи илму ирфон. Ёддошт. Маърифати омузгор // №11. 2018. С.57-61.

sentenced to death would cause the prisoners to protest and revolt. And it can be assumed that they were forced to delay the execution of this criminal sentence for a certain period of time. Otherwise, they could have acted as they did on October 4, 1938, shooting Abdullah Qadiri, Abdurauf Fitrat, and Osman Nasir, one of the original children of the nation, and formalizing their execution on October 5. But in 1930-1931, the ground was being created for the same mass destructions, the Shura government had not yet fully strengthened its position, and in order to fully establish its rule, it did not have the courage to openly lose the great men of the nation, such as Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov and Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev. .

In the memoirs of Vadud Mahmud, Nasirkhan Tora describes Kamolkhan Toraev as a person with high potential and a mature representative of science and enlightenment in many fields. In fact, these qualities of Tora were manifested during his imprisonment, first in conversations with Wadud Mahmud, then in high mathematics debates with a Russian engineer, and finally in questions and answers about medical diagnosis and treatment with a Jewish doctor. wrote that he surprised the experts.

Vadud Mahmud describes that dark night when Nasirkhan Tora Kamolkhan Toraev was taken to prison: "One night, after everyone slept according to their custom, the iron door of the room where we were sleeping opened silently... I woke up before everyone else.

- "Which one is Kamolov?" they asked me.
- I showed.
- "Wake up," they said.
- "Wake up yourself," I said.
- They pulled his leg. "Subhanallah" he stood up.
- - Pick up your things - they said: He gathered his things and went out. "Tish!"- "Tish!"- came a voice from outside, meaning the command "Shut up!".

Experienced people who have seen a lot said: "They tie the hands and mouth of the prisoner who is being taken to the shooting so that he does not resist and does not raise his voice." They took him away in this state."¹⁹.

This terrible event took place in Tashkent on April 13, 1931, as indicated by B. Irzaev. Another great scientist of a nation whose day and night have been turned into the same dark night, another true child of the Motherland will be destroyed...

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